

Consultation Report: Insights from Longyearbyen for ILLUQ, ICEBERG, and ArcSolution

Funded by
the European Union

Objectives

This report summarizes the outcomes of a series of consultation meetings organized by the three EU-funded projects ArcSolution, ICEBERG, and ILLUQ in Longyearbyen, Svalbard, in August 2025. The purpose of the meetings was to **inform** the local community about the three sister projects, with a particular focus on planned activities in Longyearbyen. The meetings also aimed to **discuss** the projects and their planned activities with community members, and to **gather input and feedback**—both on the scientific work to be conducted and on how to best involve the community in the research and communicate the results back effectively. The rationale behind holding a joint meeting was to mitigate research and consultations fatigue in Longyearbyen, as well as to start the collaboration between the three projects. This report is based on notes taken by researchers from ArcSolution, ICEBERG, and ILLUQ, following informed consent from the workshop participants.

Participants

Project representatives:

ILLUQ: Arja Rautio (WP7), Ulla Timlin (WP7), Justine Ramage (WP6), Anna Vasilevskaya (WP6), Alexandra Meyer (WP5), Hanne H. Christiansen (WP3 and 8, online).

ArcSolution: Irene Andreassen, Roland Kallenborn, Julia Olsen, Lars Otto Reiersen, Jon Øyvind Odland, Katrin Vorkamp, Riitta-Marja Leinonen, Arja Rautio, Hin Hoarau Heemstra, Helena Gonzales Lindberg.

ICEBERG: Pamela Lesser, Vanessa Lampe.

Participants at permafrost projects meeting, 27 August:

PermaMeteoCommunity – Hanne H. Christiansen, UNIS; **PCCH-Arctic** – Alexandra Meyer, Uni Vienna & Anatoly Sinitsyn, SINTEF; **EU ClimaRest** – Anatoly Sinitsyn, SINTEF & Ingebrigt Uglem, NINA; **PermaRich & InSAR Svalbard** – Line Rouyet, NORCE; **PLEISTOWEDGE** – Marjolaine Verret, UNIS; **NITRIRUN** – Marjolaine Verret, UNIS; **GAP-ST** – Andy Hodson, UNIS; **Methane entering Isdammen** – Geert Hensgens, UNIS; **Arctic Passion** – Ilkka Matero, SIOS; **LongyearObs** – Marius Jonassen, UNIS; **PermaIntern** – Hanne H. Christiansen, UNIS, in addition to ILLUQ, ArcSolution, and ICEBERG.

Participants at consultation meeting afternoon:

11 external participants from different local institutions: Longyearbyen Lokalstyre, Svalbard Science Forum (RCN), Association of Arctic Expedition Cruise Operators (AECO), Longyearbyen school, Longyearbyen Folkehøgskole, Where2O, GeoKolibri Services, The University Centre in Svalbard (UNIS)).

Participants at public meeting evening: 34 external participants.

Consultation setup

Permafrost projects meeting – UNIS and online, Tuesday 27 August:

Svalbard is a hub for permafrost studies in various disciplines. A crucial part of community consultations is to connect with colleagues working on similar topics, many of whom live in Svalbard. The meeting gathered representatives from 12 permafrost research projects in addition to ILLUQ, ArcSolution, and ICEBERG. The aim of this meeting was to gather the permafrost research community in Svalbard to share about ongoing projects and exchange knowledge, as well as to introduce the three EU projects to our colleagues. In short presentations, the participants introduced their projects and shared updates on their work. This session provided an excellent overview of ongoing research and set the stage for future collaborations.

Consultation meeting with invited stakeholders – UNIS, Wednesday 28 August, afternoon:

Over 60 invitations were sent out to different organizations, authorities, and businesses in Longyearbyen to join this meeting at UNIS. A total of 11 participants attended. During the meeting, we first introduced the objectives and planned activities in Svalbard of ILLUQ, ArcSolution, and ICEBERG, and gave the participants the chance to get to know both the projects and the researchers. We then opened the floor to discussion. We used the tool Learn Lab to gather input and structured the discussion around the following questions: *What are your concerns related to pollution, health, and permafrost? What are specific pollutants of concern? How can the projects best address these concerns? What are your wishes and needs (for data, results...)? All projects plan to have spin-off activities involving the participation of locals in monitoring and data collection – do you have any ideas or suggestions for this? How would you like to receive information from the projects/how should we communicate back our results?*

Public meeting & participatory mapping – UNIS, Wednesday 28 August, evening

Later in the evening, we held a public meeting at UNIS, which attracted 34 attendees. Invitations to the meeting had been published in the local newspaper Svalbardposten, on Facebook, as well as on flyers distributed around town. In the lecture hall Møysalen, we first presented the three projects, before opening the floor for a broader discussion focused on two central questions (again using Learn Lab): *What are your concerns regarding pollution, health, and permafrost? How can our research projects benefit you? (e.g., through involvement, data sharing, or results dissemination).* After the meeting, we served coffee, tea and snacks in the UNIS cafeteria, and participants were invited to contribute to a participatory mapping exercise led by the ILLUQ team. The aim of the exercise was to map local land-use practices and important places to the community in and around Longyearbyen. The collected information was complemented in the following days with an online participatory mapping survey.

Follow-up meetings and fieldwork – Thursday 29 August - Sunday 8 September

Consultation meetings only attract parts of the community, and a crucial part of any consultation process is thus to reach out to other actors and groups in individual meetings. After the meetings, the researchers met with several stakeholders individually, in follow-up meetings but also with people who had not attended any of the meetings. This report only contains the outcomes from the meetings held together with ArcSolution and ICEBERG.

Outcomes

What are your concerns related to pollution, health, and permafrost?

Overlapping topics from the stakeholder and public meetings:

- Water quality:
 - The water situation in Longyearbyen is considered a critical problem
 - Water quality monitoring is considered crucial
 - There are concerns about drinking water quality and safety, particularly regarding manganese and fluor, but also other pollution and contaminants
- Air quality:
 - Is a great concern, but is not being frequently discussed
 - Car exhaust from idling
 - Exhaust from the power plant: Longyearbyen has recently transitioned from coal to diesel fuel, and the resulting emissions are a significant concern for the community. The exhaust stack used for coal was much taller, allowing emissions to disperse more effectively. In contrast, diesel fumes are released from a lower height, making them more noticeable—both visibly and through their strong odor. This is especially bad in winter.
- Waste management:
 - Concerns about old and newer dump site locations and solid waste collection—is this safe? What are the impacts for the environment and people?
 - A significant portion of Longyearbyen's waste is today exported to the mainland—prompting concerns about the sustainability of this practice.
 - Missing wastewater treatment facilities—the release of wastewater into the fjord is a great concern
- Concerns related to pollution:
 - Pollution due to mining (mine tailings and dumping of coal burning residue)
 - Pollution from closed mines and other infrastructure—affects humans, wildlife, ecosystems
 - Soil pollution
 - Remobilization of pollutants
 - High CO₂ release (Arctic amplification)

- Emissions from aviation
- Release of pollutants from melting glaciers
- Remediation options for ubiquitous pollution?
- Unknown aspects (compounds with unknown effects, combination effects, long-term accumulation thresholds, and pollution cocktails)
- Accumulation of pollutants and "cocktail effects" over time
- Remobilization
- Concerns about contaminants and its impacts on animal health, biodiversity, and humans
- Animal / wildlife / ecosystem health:
 - Animal health and biodiversity – what is the role of contaminants?
 - Ecosystem disruption
 - Changes in nature due to environmental impacts
- Permafrost thaw:
 - Safety concerns due to permafrost thaw and infrastructure failure
 - Permafrost thaw and melting glaciers → what contaminants are set free and how does this impact animals and humans?
 - Landslides a great safety concern, affects recreation activities in nature
- Cultural heritage vs. general waste:
 - In Svalbard, all objects and structures older than 1945 are automatically protected as cultural heritage, resulting in a large number of historical objects and structures scattered across the islands.
 - Reindeer are frequently getting entangled in nets and ropes at beaches (happens a lot, every 3rd net that was left at the beach had a dead reindeer entangled in a recent survey, a local reports)
- Marine litter:
 - Nets “lost” at sea is a great concern.

Specific concerns from stakeholder meeting:

- Permafrost thaw and effects on housing, infrastructure, natural hazards.

Specific concerns from public meeting:

- Human health:
 - Long-range pollutants, (PFAS) on human health
 - Long-term sickness
- Health care:
 - Counselling for locals is needed, particularly during dark season. There is currently no permanent psychologist in town.
 - There is limited health care offer in Longyearbyen and a lack of continuity in the healthcare (doctors and nurses) sector.
- Increased tourism activity

- Plastics:
 - Macroplastics: Fisheries are the problem for macro-plastics
 - Microplastics in blood (women's health)
- The alcoholism and rape in Longyearbyen—these issues should be addressed officially.

Wishes and needs in terms of data and results

Overlapping wishes and needs from the stakeholder and public meetings:

- Mapping of emissions
- Animal health:
 - The health of dogs (of which there are many in Longyearbyen) is a great concern. What is the impact for dogs to drink the water? There is an impression that dogs in Svalbard have epilepsy more frequently than on the mainland. The projects could take samples of the dogs that die.
 - Are there areas where animals/organisms are more contaminated? The Polar Institute collects samples from hunters, such as reindeer jaws.

Specific wishes and needs from stakeholder meeting:

- Knowledge for land-use and urban planning:
 - Longyearbyen has a lot of old houses; almost all old houses need to be reevaluated in terms of safety. Also, most are on (too short) old wooden piles. There is a need for information about permafrost and ground conditions to renovate the buildings. How will the permafrost in Longyearbyen develop in the next decades?
 - The land-use plan for Longyearbyen is being revised. Knowledge about climate hazards is needed.
- How far do pollutants spread? (measure lengths) transect measurements, length measurements
- Warming scenarios and what this means for local permafrost conditions
- Mapping of critical areas and hazards—for individual use and land use planning
- Modeling of the flux
- There already is a mapping of pollutants in the ground and the results should be applied and reported when applying for a permit. It's not clear if the mapping information is accessible.
- Acquisition of time series data
- Mapping of seasonal changes
- Research on health needs to account for the unstable population/high turnover/general short length of stay.
- Hormones

- Time series
- Information on pathways

Specific wishes and needs from public meeting:

- Drinking water:
 - Monitoring and studying drinking water contamination? (e.g. manganese, fluoride contamination that recently occurred)
- Air quality:
 - Air monitoring is needed, especially during winter. Cold motors standing around, busses not turning off engines. Cold diesel is emitting cancerous substances. How can we address the problem of engines running? Is this addressed and how?
- Wastewater:
 - A solution needs to be found for the wastewater issue in Longyearbyen, as it is currently being discharged directly into the fjord.
 - The filter for the wastewater and pipes needs to be upgraded.
- Monitoring:
 - How is this addressed, and how do we include the existing long-term data? We have control on the available information to get a comprehensive picture. It is important to build on what is available.
 - There is a need for long-term monitoring of development of different aspects of nature and the community.
 - Different results from recent residents and long-term residents?
- Remediation of land and water potentials
- What can we do individually for the environment? Research projects can help identifying ways to support the environment in every-day life.
- Identify litter and pollution hotspots (both for locals and communicate them to policy makers), including marine litter hot spots.
- Nano-plastics
 - Will this be looked into?
 - Are there remediation strategies regarding nanoplastics?
- Beach and coast clean-ups are effective and a fun way to engage people, there should be more of those
 - Forlandet is a pollution hotspot (due to currents).

Needs and wishes in terms of dissemination

Overlapping dissemination needs and wishes from the stakeholder and public meetings

- Open, easy access and well-documented data. Transparency in results.

- There is an experienced lack of transparency—research projects can help creating new knowledge and making that knowledge available.
- Results should be disseminated in different ways and formats to reach as many as possible.
 - Focus on popular-scientific communication of the results (e.g. newspaper).
 - Regular briefs for the public should be made available by the projects. The communication officer at Lokalstyret could assist in feeding information about the projects into Lokalstyret's *Innbyggerapp* (citizen app).
 - Access to interactive maps and easy-to-read documents.
- Language:
 - Information should be easily accessible in a streamlined way without jargon and abbreviations (this point came up often!), also that tourist guides can use it.
 - Dissemination of results and data in a way that is easy to understand: newsletters for communication and dissemination; summary of publications, make available on website; mapping tool can be fed into existing mapping systems.
 - Maps and communication material must be understandable.
 - There are research reports available (amap.no). These need to be translated, condensed, and made available by scientists for the general public and inhabitants. Factsheet, shorter representation of knowledge on Svalbard (popular science summaries).
- Communication about water and air quality:
 - Availability of data water and air quality (via an app?) so locals can understand what is going on. There is a perceived lack of transparency in the community regarding water quality, people don't know what is going on and this causes great concern.
- Dialogue and collaboration:
 - Shorten the distance between common personal concerns and policy makers.
 - Communicate the problems that stand out also to local authorities, motivate them to take actions.
 - Shorten the distance between personal concerns and policy makers—create spaces for communication.
 - Challenge: long-term commitment and the problem of high turnover of population and staff in Longyearbyen—challenges science-society collaborations.
- Citizen science:
 - Local institutions should be involved in research and coordinated with!
 - UNIS, Folkehøgskolen, Lokalstyret etc.
 - Interest in participating in research projects.

Specific input regarding dissemination from stakeholder meeting:

- One place/source to find it all:
 - Information from research projects should be shared on some platform that is easily accessible.
 - There are many projects connected to Svalbard. Looking for different sources is time consuming. Nobody will go through all the individual project webpages.
 - → There should be one place to find relevant information from all the three projects, for instance on the UNIS or Lokalstyre webpage.
 - Results and knowledge could be disseminated on the Lokalstyre app (in an understandable language).
 - Because of the high turnover of the population in Longyearbyen, a regularly updated platform with information about pollution and other issues could be established. This could be in the form of a basic Q&A list, with questions of residents. This could be posted on Lokalstyret's website or in the citizen app. The projects should pass on relevant information to different platforms.
 - Often similar questions are asked repeatedly—how can we address them? Official channel for answering questions and provide information about pollution and health in Svalbard.
- Thematic pages for use in education would be useful.
- Social science results are useful for knowledge-based planning.
- Different pollution maps of Longyearbyen would be a useful way to display pollution-themed research.
- Time series and possibilities to combine the data.
- There was also a conversation around the local knowledge of pollutants, i.e. mine tailings. More information is needed on this that can be disseminated onto a platform.
- There is a clear wish for a meeting at the end of the projects to communicate results—BUT it should be shorter than three hours.

What are specific pollutants of concern?

(stakeholder meeting only)

- Diesel (from the power plant)
- Mining waste
- Micro-plastics
- Medications in the sea / pharmaceuticals (antidepressants, painkillers): how do fish take up the chemical components from pharmaceuticals? How does it affect the people who eat fish?
- Rubber particles

- Plastic additives
- Heavy metals
- Styrofoam
- Lead from hunting
- Whatever in H₂O
- Products of burning
- Rubber particles
- Products of burning
- General contaminants in drinking water
- Painkillers

Other questions and input to the projects

Do the three projects coordinate their sampling strategy (match locations and share samples)? This could help obtaining a more complete dataset.

The projects are in the starting phase and have started the dialogue on how to share the data and coordinate the activities. The coordination of the projects was not done in planning phase; now is the time to synchronize activities. The projects work on different types of pollution (i.e. large plastics and microplastics) and in different complementary locations. The multitude of field sites offer a good opportunity to get a spatially more complete picture. Different locations will in a way increase the results, making them more comprehensive when developing the overall picture of the research topics.

Do you collaborate with existing initiatives and clean-up projects?

ICEBERG connects with existing initiatives and clean-ups. People would love to join these efforts, since usually such cruises are expensive.

How do you acquire data on ship emissions?

In ICEBERG, AES data from ships will be used for modelling. We will collect ecosystem PAMs, ASTD data, field measurements, and plankton ecosystem modelling based on different types of pollution scenarios.

Citizen science activities

All three projects have planned citizen science activities, and collaborations between the schools in Longyearbyen (high schools (ungdomsskole and vgs.) and Folkehøgskolen) and the projects were discussed. Practical involvement in research activities can enhance student learning and generates ideas. The three projects should combine data sets and work with schools to integrate into curriculums. Students could then use the data for school projects, and also participate in the three projects (it is more interesting for students to be part of measurements and analyses as part of a real project). Different topics (in math, chemistry, geophysics, biology, social sciences) could be addressed. Connecting people from different

age-groups (high school classes, Folkehøgskolen) is considered positive by the schools. In ArcSolution, inclusion of the school and students is included in the project plan. There is already relevant data available that can be provided for school purposes. In ILLUQ, there is also the plan to involve the schools, but the concrete activities should be co-developed with the schools. Hanne Christiansen is heading a permafrost internship program as part of the permafrost citizen science activities.

Pollutants

PCBs: organic chemical used in paintings and isolating materials. Even if banned 50 years ago, it is still in nature. The half time in humans is 50 years. ArcSolution will record the concentrations in humans. Screening: strategy for the population. How many samples do we need to say something about the whole population? What is the effect of the number of years staying in one place? The instability of the population will be taken into account. There is existing knowledge available, and the local community board (Lokalstyre) would like to help. The data will be available for the projects.

Next steps

Consultations are not one-time events but a process. Next steps involve maintaining dialogue with existing contacts regarding specific issues (for instance the planning department at Lokalstyre regarding the results from the mapping exercise). This report will be made publicly available. The collaboration between ILLUQ, ArcSolution, and ICEBERG is already being followed up. The input gathered regarding citizen science activities in Svalbard is discussed among the three projects and we are working on joint citizen science projects. First results and progress will be presented in a community workshop in Longyearbyen in 2025, most probably at the next ArcSolution community workshop.

Responsible author and contact: Alexandra Meyer (University of Vienna / Western Norway Research Institute, ILLUQ), alexandra.meyer@univie.ac.at

**Funded by
the European Union**